

**HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN: THEORETICAL BASIS,
DEMOGRAPHIC OPPORTUNITIES AND STRATEGIES FOR SUSTAINABLE
ECONOMIC GROWTH**

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Annotation. This scientific article analyzes the theoretical-evolutionary development of the concept of human capital, its role in sustainable economic growth, and the possibilities for effectively utilizing the demographic dividend emerging under the conditions of Uzbekistan. The article evaluates the share of human capital in national wealth, recent changes in education, healthcare, and vocational fields, as well as budget allocations and institutional reforms within the framework of the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy, based on data from the World Bank, OECD, and the UN. According to the research results, it is substantiated that the country can enter the ranks of upper-middle-income economies through the qualitative development of human capital, the integration of digital skills, the formation of a lifelong education system, and the elimination of regional inequality.

Keywords. human capital, demographic dividend, sustainable economic growth, educational reforms, professional skills, lifelong learning, "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy, World Bank index, labor market, digital transformation.

Human capital is one of the priority tasks of the government of any country. Based on this, it is important for every country to create all the necessary conditions for the younger generation to take a worthy place in society in the future and become competitive personnel, acquiring knowledge and skills that will help them achieve success in life. The development of human capital is a set of comprehensive measures and is carried out within the framework of long-term and specifically aimed tasks. After all, today every country primarily strives to enhance human capital, that is, to increase the intellectual potential of the nation. Currently, 60 percent of the population of Uzbekistan consists of young people, and half of them are women. According to expert analysis, by 2048, the number of able-bodied people in our country will increase significantly. As a result, the country can receive a valuable demographic dividend. It should be noted that this opportunity must be used effectively. In the recently adopted "Uzbekistan – 2030" Strategy, the development of the social sphere is defined as a priority task. Accordingly, the draft state budget for 2024 pays great attention to these areas. In particular, this year 102.5 trillion UZS were allocated for the development of human capital. This is 15% more than in 2023.

These funds are mainly allocated to the following areas:

- Modernization of preschool and general education infrastructure;
- Financing higher education and scientific research;
- Expansion of vocational education centers and their integration with employers;
- Digitalization of the healthcare system and strengthening primary healthcare;
- Expanding social protection networks and introducing targeted assistance mechanisms.

According to the President's instructions, in 2022-2026, it is planned to achieve inclusive and sustainable economic growth, develop human capital, and reduce poverty by at least 2 times. In foreign countries, investments in human capital are also considered an important factor in increasing competitiveness and ensuring economic growth at the micro and macro levels.

An important condition for ensuring the sustainable development of the economy is the consistent implementation of a strategy aimed at improving the quality of human capital and improving people's professional skills and experience through lifelong learning. During the

World Bank's study of the structure of global national wealth using 141 countries as an example, it was revealed that the share of human capital in its total value is 64%, and its volume has increased by 55% over the last 20 years. In high-income countries that are members of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), the share of human capital in national wealth was 70%, while in low-income countries, its share was 41%. It is the differences in human capital that determine the competitiveness of the country's economy in the global market, the well-being of the population, and, in general, the differences in human development; in particular, 10–30% of the differences in per capita income between countries are determined by the fact that they are explained by human capital. It should be noted that economic growth factors are changing today. Instead of traditional factors (labor, land, capital, entrepreneurial ability), science and education, that is, in general, the factors that are the intellect of the nation, come to the fore. The entire world is witnessing that Uzbekistan will resolutely continue the policy of building a New Uzbekistan—a legal, secular, democratic, and social state—and that our country is confidently moving along the path of fundamental reforms aimed at strengthening the principles of democracy and justice based on the noble idea "For the sake of human honor and dignity." As a result of consistent reforms and policies aimed at improving the people's standard of living, poverty in our country has halved since 2017, and by 2030, it is planned to reduce this figure by another 7 percent, and the scale of healthcare, education, and other social services will be increased several times over. "The development of human capital and the upbringing of a creative young generation is one of the strategic tasks that Uzbekistan has set for itself," the President emphasized. "We consider accessible and quality education for all to be the most effective factor in eradicating poverty, improving the well-being of the people, and achieving sustainable economic growth." In recent years, our country has accumulated extensive experience in this regard - the education system is undergoing fundamental changes. Over the past six years, enrollment in preschool education has increased from 21 to 70 percent, and in higher education from 9 to 38 percent. By 2030, every child will be able to attend kindergarten, and every second school graduate will have the opportunity to study at a university. Today, we can observe a growing interest in studying the impact of human capital on the processes of ensuring the socio-economic development of the country. In particular, numerous scientific studies have been conducted and are being conducted by major international organizations and institutions such as the UN, the World Bank, and the IMF. However, certain uncertainties remain in defining the category of "human capital" and assessing its impact on economic growth; at the same time, its components have not yet been fully clarified, and the impact of human capital on the economic growth and innovative development of the national economy has not been quantified. In the context of the emergence of new economic relations, many research works are being carried out on the methodology of using human capital to ensure economic growth in the national economy and ensuring its quality, including in May 2022, the World Bank for the second time published a systematic diagnostic study of the country for Uzbekistan. It contains recommendations for the government to remove barriers to private sector growth, limit state participation in the economy, develop human capital, and transition the country to a "green" economy. Since Uzbekistan has set itself the goal of becoming one of the countries with an above-average income by 2030, one of the main goals is to increase real GDP per capita by an average of 10 percent per year. This, in turn, implies limiting state intervention in the economy and the accelerated development of the private sector. Furthermore, it sets tasks for the government to consistently invest in human capital, a strong social protection system, and a green growth model. At the same time, in the context of establishing new economic relations, serious requirements are put forward, such as the need for employees to strive to increase their level of knowledge regarding the implementation of labor activities and to be able to use modern technologies. At the same time, in practice, there are problems such as an insufficient level of

knowledge and professional skills of workers, and a shortage of personnel, which holds back the growth of labor productivity and industrial production. Changes in technical and technological processes, new requirements imposed by employers on workers amid intensifying globalization processes, a decline in the quality of training for future specialists, and the impossibility for them, for one reason or another, of raising their level of knowledge (lack of interest from employers in improving the professional level of low-skilled workers) can lead to such problems. In short, the formation of human capital as an important factor in ensuring economic growth, its effective use, and the study of factors affecting the quality of human capital are among the pressing problems of our time. In particular, the following factors that are important in terms of influencing the level of human capital formation, its commercialization, and its utilization can be highlighted separately:

- innate individual abilities;
- the level of education of parents;
- social status of the population; - tax policy;
- cultural and ideological factors.

To raise the level of qualitative development of human capital to a higher level, it is proposed to systematically implement the following:

- supporting entrepreneurship and strengthening the role of the private sector in the economy, improving the investment and healthy competitive environment;
- developing the infrastructure of each mahalla in order to improve the quality of life and living conditions of the population;
- improving the quality of vocational education to fully cover the poor and needy segments of the population with a targeted social protection system, involving them in entrepreneurship through vocational training;
- ensuring macroeconomic stability in the country;
- development of innovative educational processes for young people.

The World Bank's 2022 systemic diagnostics also recommended removing barriers to the private sector, optimizing state participation in the economy, increasing investment in human capital, and transitioning to a "green economy." These requirements are fully consistent with Uzbekistan's strategy to join the ranks of upper-middle-income countries by 2030.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the sustainable development of the modern economy depends directly on human capital; therefore, consistent policies in the field of human resource development at the regional level and at the state level as a whole, as well as balanced investments in human capital, are necessary. Furthermore, the formation, development, and management of human capital, as well as the implementation of innovative transformations and support for human capital, play a strategically crucial role in ensuring environmental, economic stability, and social well-being. In recent years, the republic has increasingly focused on human development, as traditional economic ideas and concepts based on maximizing profit from limited resources, including natural resources, labor, and capital, are losing their relevance day by day.

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